

Digital Reading Habits and Attention Span: A Study of Students of Govt. Aizawl College, Mizoram

Zorinpuia¹, R.K. Ngurtinkhuma²

¹ *Research Scholar, Department of Library & Information Science, Mizoram University, Aizawl.*

² *Professor, Department of Library & Information Science, Mizoram University, Aizawl.*

Abstract— This study investigates the digital reading habits and attention spans of college students at Government Aizawl College (GAC) in Mizoram. With the increasing integration of digital tools in education, understanding their impact and influence on reading behaviors and academic performance is necessary. Data was collected from 116 students, equally divided between those who prefer digital and print reading. The results indicate significant differences in comprehension, eye strain, and attentive abilities between the two mediums. Print reading generally leads to better text comprehension and less eye strain, while digital reading offers better accessibility and ease of multitasking. Although the gender-based preferences of print and digital format are not high, the study revealed that males are more inclined towards print, whereas more females show preference for digital reading. The study underscores the need for educational strategies and curriculum that can benefit both formats of reading in colleges. The study stresses on the importance of utilizing digital tools in remote places like Mizoram where digitization is rapidly advancing and is becoming easily accessible. The study acts as a powerful tool for understanding the reading habits and reading culture in remote areas using digital resources, where further comparative studies will be needed to better understand the long-term impact of digitization.

Keywords— Digital reading, Reading habits, Attention span, College students, Mizoram, Reading preference

I. INTRODUCTION

With the integration of digital tools and resources in every aspect of our daily lives, the reading and writing of students, researchers and scholars also tend to lean heavily towards digital materials as technology advances. Although digital reading materials do not yet seem to contribute a vast majority of readers' preference, it is steadily growing especially with the ease of use and continuous developments and technological improvements. However, as recent studies suggest, many young adults still seem to prefer paper-based resources for reading of complex subjects (Ocal, Durgunoglu & Twite, 2022)[1]. While digital reading materials have not yet eclipsed traditional print resources in readers' preferences, their significance in academia and daily life cannot be overstated. The convenience and accessibility offered by digital tools have led to a steady rise in their adoption across various disciplines (Mirza et al., 2021)[2]. In fact, recent years have witnessed a notable surge in the availability and sophistication of digital resources with innovative platforms and technologies continually enhancing the digital reading experience. As a result, scholars, researchers, and students find themselves increasingly reliant on digital materials for a wide array of subjects and disciplines. With the growth of the internet and mobile devices, access to information is becoming easier but leads to a more unstructured form of reading habits, where readers prefer short and non-linear texts (Loan, 2011)[3]. In order to maintain good reading skills and deep reading ability, it is important to maintain a good balance between reading on digital devices and reading in print (Baron, 2015)[4].

Mizoram is a small state in the far north-eastern region of India with a population of around 11 lakhs. With Aizawl as the capital city of Mizoram, Govt. Aizawl College (GAC) is one of the largest and most significant colleges in Mizoram. Established in 1975, GAC is regarded as one of the most important institutions in Mizoram and has played a pivotal role to the youth of the state. The college has produced a host of influential and distinguished list of alumni who have become successful and important figures and leaders in many facets of life. The college and its students provide as an excellent sample for studying the college student population of the state. The college has approximately 1000 students and offers courses on

Bachelor of Arts with core in English, Mizo, History, Political Science, Education, Economics, Sociology, Hindi and Bachelors in Commerce.

II. DIGITAL AND PRINT READING

Reading through traditional print format and reading through digital devices creates trends and habits on readers which differ in various ways. It has been observed that reading through these two different means affects the comprehension of the texts being read or studied. Reading on paper generally leads to better comprehension on most readers (Singer & Alexander, 2017a)[5]. The same study has also given important results on the difference of eye strain and physical comfort level, as well as reading time and efficiency in reading where reading on print has an advantage for readers in most cases. Reading on paper and print format is generally perceived to be better as it involves higher need for sensory engagement and introduces less distractions to the readers than when done on screen (Jabr, 2013)[6]. Physical and tangible feedback available using print format is also an important factor in reading with less distractions towards the reader, creating better comprehension, focus and attention (Mangen, Walgermo, & Bronnick, 2013)[7].

Reading on digital formats is easier and is more accessible to various materials and resources. Multitasking while reading, although possible while reading in print format, is far more common among digital readers and is more manageable (Larhmaid, 2018)[8]. Due to the availability and accessibility of numerous resources online, as well as the ease of storage using digital devices, reading on digital devices creates numerous benefits.

With the ever-rising use of digital tools and devices in day-to-day life, college students fall under the age range of those who most frequently use these digital devices and technology. Although the use of digital devices has increased, their beneficial utility may not be so high. It is especially important to have such knowledge in remote places like Mizoram. The digital and print reading habits and its implications on the attention span of college students in remote places like Mizoram may or may not be similar to larger, more metropolitan places where such studies have been conducted.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

As per the study conducted by Bresó-Grancha, Jorques-Infante & Moret-Tatay (2022)[9], the time efficiency of digital reading cannot be downplayed. The study shows that the latency for reading through digital devices was lower than reading using print medium. However, the study was not conclusive, word and phrasal recognition and understanding was slightly higher when reading through print medium than it is on digital mediums.

Benedetto, et al. (2013)[10] found that prolonged reading on LCD screens result in higher visual fatigue. While new technology adopts better forms of filters and anti-glare technologies, there are issues in readers related to backlight technology. The LCD displays have been found to be associated with impaired reading performances. A subsequent study by Benedetto, et al. (2014)[11] studied the effects of luminance and illuminance on visual fatigue and arousal where they found that higher levels of screen luminance increase the readers' visual fatigue and higher levels of screen luminance or ambient illuminance increases the arousal of the readers.

A study by Mizrachi, et al. (2018)[12] finds that among university students, a vast majority prefer to read using print materials for academic reading. While using print materials for reading, the study finds that the participants have better focus and show greater retention of information on what they read. The participants also largely prefer print materials for reading long texts. This paper, which studies university students worldwide, shows that demographic differences do not amount to much difference in the reading preference of students.

Foasberg, (2014)[13] discovers that among college students, when comparing the use of print and electronic devices for reading, students' preference for academic and leisure reading leans towards print and electronic mediums respectively. Most participants of the study preferred to read in print for academic

and long form reading, electronic format is the preferred choice for reading of nonacademic articles. Non-academic reading of print format is mainly for reading magazines and fiction books, while reading through electronic devices other than nonacademic materials is mainly for reading short form of fiction.

Hooper and Herath (2014)[14] find that among university students, there is drastic growth in online reading due to the growth of online materials, where students show an increase in reading speed and the ability to skim through texts easily. However, this growth also comes with negative impacts on readers where they are shown to be more easily distracted, lose patience in their reading more easily and experience more eye strain. Participants also seem to scan and skim through online materials without going through the texts. This is in contrast to reading in print where more than 80 percent of the participants read through books and other materials from beginning to end.

According to a study conducted by Singer & Alexander (2017b)[15], students' self-assessment of their reading between digital and print mediums showed equal ability to identify the general ideas of texts they read. The study however shows that students tend to exaggerate their reading performance while reading digitally. Students could remember and recall important points from the texts they read better when they are reading using print mediums.

While reading on digital format has probable negative effects on eye strain, comprehension and attention span, Liu (2005)[16] also notes the efficiency of digital tools and reading materials offering better convenience for readers in terms of access and reach. Digital reading also offers better efficiency of time, space and overall availability.

A study by Jeong (2012)[17] found that, when comparing e-books to print books, print books have an incredible effect on the quiz scores of children, while e-books use leads to greater eye strain and fatigue. However, the students were satisfied with reading e-books although they prefer print books for studying. E-books and digital mediums of reading materials are useful in their ability to have interactive and accessible features.

IV. SIGNIFICANCE AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

With digital tools and resources rapidly increasing and being integrated into modern learning environments, it is crucial to understand the digital reading habits and attention spans among college students who are most prone to the use of digital tools. This study focuses on the students of GAC in Mizoram which can be seen, especially to the outside eye, as a more backward and reclusive part of the world. However, the growth of digitization around the world and its accessibility to anyone marks the need to understand its impact on the youth. Insight into the impacts of reading comprehension, attention span, academic performance and other factors under digital reading as compared to print reading is essential. It is irrefutable that reliance on digital resources is growing rapidly, which gives rise to the need for understanding the pros and cons of digital tools and resources on college students for their academic learning and general learning abilities. Finding reliable data on such cases can help educational practices to better suit the needs of students in remote areas like Mizoram, and to understand how to better provide advantageous digital resources to such areas.

This study covers the reading preference and habits of college students studying in GAC where surveys are made to understand what number and which group can best represent the population of the college. It includes a comparative analysis of print and digital reading preferences, the duration and frequency of reading sessions as well as the physical and cognitive effects associated with each reading format. The study also covers the opinions of students who have the format they least prefer so as to understand how each medium is better or worse, and how they may be addressed for further studies.

V. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study has four objectives as below:

- i. To identify the reading habits and practices of print and digital readers.

- ii. To study the difference in attention span between print and digital format readers.
- iii. To determine the advantages and disadvantages of print and digital medium of reading.
- iv. To explore the ways in which both print and digital mediums of reading may be improved.

VI. METHODOLOGY

In order to gather data that accurately represents the student body of GAC, a questionnaire was designed judiciously and was administered online to the participants to respond at their own leisure time. The questionnaire separates the answers of those who preferred reading physical books to those who prefer reading on digital devices. The questionnaire however included similar questions which reflect various aspects of their reading habits according to their reading preference.

The questionnaire includes such questions as the participants' ability to concentrate for long periods of time, their proclivity to taking breaks while studying and many other factors. Through this comprehensive collected data, the objectives of the study were expressed with the highest possible confidence level. The data from this survey was analyzed using descriptive statistics. Comparative results found through this survey have been presented to showcase the various levels of reading capabilities and effectiveness of such participants.

VII. DISCUSSIONS AND FINDINGS

A. General Information

Data for the study was gathered from 116 students enrolled at GAC. The survey took 58 students each for those who prefer reading digital over print, and those who prefer print over digital resources, to make up a combined population of 116 students. Among the participants, 10 (8.6%) were below 18 years old, the majority, comprising 90 students (77.58%), were aged between 19 and 20 years and 16 (13.79%) were above of 21 years old. All participants were in their 2nd semester pursuing a Bachelor of Arts degree at the time of data collection.

The gender distribution of the participants also revealed a composition of 56 (48.27%) male and 60 (51.72%) female students. Upon examination of the 58 students each of those who prefer print and those who prefer digital reading materials, we see that out of those who prefer print reading materials, 32 students (55.17%) are male while 26 (44.82%) are female. In contrast, out of the 58 students who prefer digital reading only 24 students (41.37%) are male while 34 (58.62%) are female. This indicates that 57% of male participants prefer reading in print over digital resources, while only 43% of all female participants prefer print media. This finding suggests that females may be more inclined to digital reading, where more than half of the males prefer print reading. This data is shown in Table 1.

TABLE I
GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF READING PREFERENCE

<i>Reading Preferences</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total</i>
Print	32 (27.58%)	26 (22.41%)	58 (50%)
Digital	24 (20.68%)	34 (29.31%)	58 (50%)
Total	56 (48.27%)	60 (51.72%)	116 (100%)

Source: Survey data

B. Reading Time

Looking at the reading duration span of participants in a single session, it is evident that those who prefer print reading tend to read longer hours than digital resources. Out of the total participants, 18 (15.51%) print readers read less than 1 hour in a session while 31 (26.72%) digital readers read less than 1 hour in a session. When looking at the participants who read for a period of 1-2 hours and 2-3 hours, there are 38 (32.75%) print readers while there are only 24 (20.68%) digital readers. This shows that while a majority of students who prefer digital reading spend less than an hour while reading, more than half of the

respondents who prefer print reading spend between 1 to 3 hours in a single sitting (Table 2). The reading time of print readers are shown to be longer on average.

TABLE II
READING DURATION

<i>Duration</i>	<i>Print</i>	<i>Digital</i>	<i>Total</i>
> 1 hour	18 (15.51%)	31 (26.72%)	49 (42.24%)
1-2 hours	28 (24.13%)	19 (16.37%)	47 (40.51%)
2-3 hours	10 (8.62%)	5 (4.31%)	15 (12.93%)
< 3 hours	2 (1.72%)	3 (2.58%)	5 (4.31%)
Total	58 (50%)	58 (50%)	116 (100%)

Source: Survey data

C. Reading Frequency

The data on the frequency of reading sessions observed by the students is different, where more students who read using digital mediums read daily as compared to those who prefer reading print materials (Table 3). By analyzing the data, out of the total respondents, there are 30 (25.86%) digital daily readers while 16 (13.79%) are print readers. This means that out of 58 participants in either group, 51.72% of digital readers read daily while only 27.58% of print readers read daily. Out of the total population, there are more print readers than digital readers who read 3-5 times weekly, with 18 (15.51%) digital and 12 (10.34%) print readers. Likewise, among those who read 1-2 times weekly, print readers are higher than digital readers with 20 (17.24%) and 12 (10.34%) respectively. The number of readers who read once a week or less is 4 (3.44%) participants in both groups.

TABLE III
READING FREQUENCY

<i>Duration</i>	<i>Print</i>	<i>Digital</i>	<i>Total</i>
Daily	16 (13.79%)	30 (25.86%)	46 (39.65%)
3-5 times weekly	18 (15.51%)	12 (10.34%)	30 (25.86%)
1-2 times weekly	20 (17.24%)	12 (10.34%)	32 (27.58%)
>1 time weekly	4 (3.44%)	4 (3.44%)	8 (6.89%)
Total	58 (50%)	58 (50%)	116 (100%)

Source: Survey data

The data found in Table 3 shows that more digital readers read on a daily basis. The results show a more evenly distributed data of print readers when studying their reading frequency within a week time.

D. Reading Preferences

Among both print and digital readers, the main reason for reading is for studying with 28 print (48.28%) readers and 23 digital (39.65%) readers. Reading for news and leisure reading constitute the vast remaining percentage of the reasons for reading. 10 print (17.24%) and 15 digital (25.87%) readers mainly read for news while 14 print (17.24%) and 11 digital (18.97%) readers read for pleasure. The remaining 6 print (10.34%) and 9 digital (15.51%) readers mainly read for some other reasons. Cross-reading between the two mediums of reading is common among the participants where only 4 students (6.9%) of each group state that they rarely or never use the other medium for reading. This means that 54 students (93%) of each group do read on their less preferred format of reading.

E. Attention Span

The attention span and factors determining higher or lower attention span among readers is studied by examining the ways in which those who prefer each medium of reading sits through reading sessions. Both groups, those who prefer print and those who prefer digital materials, experience the urge to take breaks and also experience eye strains while reading. Among the respondents of both groups, eye strain is a common occurrence while reading. However, more digital readers report a higher case of eye strain

experienced with 35 individuals (60.34%) affected, while out of the print readers 26 participants (45.82%) report that they also experience regular eye strain while reading. Participants who feel they can read for a certain period of time before they start to lose focus on what they read is distributed quite evenly among either group. Out of the 58 participants of both study groups, a total of 34 students (58.62%) who read print materials can read for 30 minutes to more than 1 hour before losing focus. This is in contrast to a total of 24 students (41.37%) who read digital materials reporting that they can read for the same duration before losing focus. The lower time duration before losing focus by both groups is also different where 24 print readers (41.37%) can read less than 15 minutes to 30 minutes before losing focus whereas 34 digital readers (58.62%) can read the same duration before losing focus and/or attention. (Table 4).

TABLE IV
FOCUSED READING DURATION

<i>How long can you read before losing focus and/or attention?</i>	<i>Print</i>	<i>Digital</i>	<i>Total</i>
>15 minutes	4(3.44%)	16(13.79%)	20(17.24%)
15-30 minutes	20(17.24%)	18(15.51%)	38(32.75%)
30-45 minutes	18(15.51%)	12(10.34%)	30(25.86%)
45-60 minutes	10(8.62%)	7(6.03%)	17(14.65%)
< 60 minutes	6(5.17%)	5(4.31%)	11(9.48%)
Total	58(50%)	58(50%)	116(100%)

Source: Survey data

Findings show that print medium readers experience fewer distractions while they are on their reading sessions. 22 (37.93%) out of the 58 print readers feel that they are never or are rarely distracted once they start reading. In contrast, only 5 (8.62%) of digital readers feel the same. While such is the case, 21 print readers and 25 digital readers (36.2% print readers and 43.1% digital readers) feel that they sometimes get distracted while reading no matter what medium they use.

Results up to this point show that print readers are more focused, are less likely to be distracted and experience less eye strain. This data may be backed up by the open-ended question on the effectiveness of the reading medium which they prefer less. 31 (53.44%) participants who prefer digital medium believe that reading in print format gives them higher concentration and better academic performance. However, they prefer reading in digital format due to its ease of use and availability of a wider array of materials online. Only 6 participants (10.34%) of digital readers find digital medium of reading to be more effective and efficient overall. On the other hand, participants who prefer print reading do not find digital format to be better in any way, with 42 (72.41%) print readers finding print to be better for academic studies and 16 (27.58%) feel that both mediums may be used equally effective if used correctly.

F. Readers' Reading Breaks

The habit of reading among print format readers tend to curve more towards reading through particular materials more thoroughly while digital readers tend to take breaks more. Out of the 58 digital readers, 33 (56.89%) participants take a high number of breaks while reading, while only 13 (22.41%) do not take much breaks during their reading sessions. On the other hand, among the 58 participating print readers, it is reported that only 10 (17.24%) print readers take a high number of breaks during their reading, while 34 (58.62%) do not take much breaks while reading (Table 5). A cross study between two sets of data which shows the difference between print and digital readers on their habits of taking breaks while reading and their tendency to manage their time when reading seems to have certain correlations. It can be observed that print readers are less inclined to taking breaks while reading than those who prefer digital reading.

TABLE V
READERS' READING BREAKS

<i>Breaks during reading</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>High</i>	<i>Total</i>
Print	34 (29.31%)	14 (12.06%)	10 (8.62%)	58 (50%)
Digital	13 (11.20%)	12 (10.34%)	33 (28.44%)	58 (50%)
Total	47 (40.51%)	26 (22.41%)	43 (37.06%)	116 (100%)

Source: Survey data

The data seen on Table 5 shows that print readers take fewer breaks. Low numbers of breaks while reading are those who rarely or only occasionally take breaks while reading. High numbers of breaks are those who cannot sit and read for a prolonged period and often gets up and takes breaks. The means of taking breaks ranges from stretching, walking and moving around, as well as breaks for mental clarity according to responses.

G. Readers' Time Management

The study finds that most print readers read through their materials until they finish certain chapters or sections on their reading materials. This is in contrast to most digital readers who do not seem to have clear time management and reading patterns as is the case with print readers. They in fact are shown to take breaks or stop reading as they feel like without setting certain goals before they take breaks.

TABLE VI
READERS' TIME MANAGEMENT

<i>Reading goal</i>	<i>Print</i>	<i>Digital</i>	<i>Total</i>
Reading goals made	36 (31.03%)	20 (17.24%)	56 (48.27%)
No reading goals	18 (15.51%)	28 (24.13%)	46 (39.65%)
Uncertain	4 (3.44%)	10 (8.62%)	14 (12.06%)
Total	58 (50%)	58 (50%)	116 (100%)

Source: Survey data

Time management data is compiled from the response on the question of the participants' habit in reading where they disclose their practice of reading through texts. The data shows that out of 58 print readers 36 (62.06%) print readers sit and read through certain predetermined set of chapters or pages before they take breaks, or set certain time periods for them to read. This is in contrast to only 20 (34.48%) digital readers who set reading goals, while 28 (48.27%) tend to not follow this habit and take breaks from reading as they feel like, without setting any goals or time frame for their reading. Among print readers, 18 (31.03%) do not set reading goals for themselves before taking breaks.

In an open-ended question posed to the participants of the study, a question is asked on whether the participants believe that reading on the format they less prefer would affect their attention span while reading differently, 44 print readers (75.86%) and 35 digital readers (60.34%) believe that reading on the other form of reading material does change their attention span in reading. 18 (31.03%) of digital readers are, however, not sure if reading on print materials would change their attention span while reading. Of those who believe it does change their attention span, print readers are of the opinion that when reading digital resources they tend to read through materials faster, but it negatively affects their text comprehension; requiring multiple reads to get the same understanding as they would get while reading on print once. Digital readers who feel reading on print changes their attention span is of the opinion that while they feel they get better resources online and more variety of resources, reading on print when done for academic purposes gives a more authentic feeling of studying, giving them a better sense of learning while reading.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study explored the digital reading habits and attention spans of college students at GAC, Mizoram. The findings reveal visible differences in the reading habits and preferences of print and digital mediums. Each medium of reading have their advantages and disadvantages which are evident from the data presented. Findings on the study suggests that print reading is more favorable for academic reading amongst college students as print reading results in longer attentive reading hours. However, the data showing that digital format readers tend to read more frequently when observed on their day to day reading results from the ease of access through digital means. While reading on print creates a habit of a more focused and attention grabbing method of reading, digital readers tend to read through more materials.

As the data shows, digital readers tend to experience more eye strain while reading and are more prone to taking breaks while reading. Print readers tend to read longer period of time without taking breaks and are less likely to be distracted while reading. However, it is important to notice that under this study, more participants who prefer digital medium tend to read on a daily basis. This can be seen as a result of the ease of access of digital media and resources. Taking into account the fact that only 4 participants (6.89%) of each group stating they never use the other format of reading, those who prefer digital reading can be seen as the group which reads more on a daily basis. This comes as a result of the fact that while also only 6.89% of print readers never use digital mediums for reading, only 15 (25.86%) read daily whereas 30 (51.72%) of digital readers read daily. If digital resources are utilized by print readers as much as digital readers, the frequency of reading done by print readers is expected to be higher, which is not the case in this study.

The findings reveal the importance of developing educational strategies that can reap the benefit of both reading formats. For example, incorporating both print and digital materials into a college's set of provided reading materials can diversify the learning preferences and improve educational excellence. Additionally, it is also crucial to be aware of the potential for eye strain which is common through prolonged digital use. It may be advisable to limit the time period students use digital devices for studying by encouraging breaks after reading long periods and by using screen filters as other studies suggest. For remote regions like Mizoram where access to digital devices is growing and quickly catching up with bigger cities, digital tools offer great opportunities for expanding educational content. However, it is also important to balance this with the cognitive and comprehensive benefits print reading offers.

Future research should explore the long-term effects of digital and print reading on academic performances and cognitive development. Additionally, examining demographic variations, such as differences in reading habits between urban and rural college students in Mizoram, can provide more insights into the trends on the subject. The knowledge of these factors will prove useful in understanding and developing effective educational practices in an increasingly digitized world where remote places like Mizoram are also affected.

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